

CNV GWAS of Seizure phenotypes in SANAD (MAF \geq 1%)

Figure 1

i

PDB 7V9M

ii

PDB 6G79

Figure 2b

PDB 7EB2

Figure 3b

Brain regions in the UKBEC study

- CRBL: Cerebellar cortex
- FCTX: Frontal cortex
- HIPP: Hippocampus
- MEDU: Medullar (inferior olivary nucleus)
- OCTX: Occipital cortex
- PUTM: Putamen
- SNIG: Substantia nigra
- TCTX: Temporal cortex
- THAL: Thalamus
- WHMT: Intralobular white matter

Brain regions in the NABEC study

- CRBL: Cerebellar cortex
- FCTX: Frontal cortex

Figure 5a

Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) analysis in UKBEC Study

Figure 5b

Chromosome 1p36

Affymetrix exon specific gene expression values in 10 brain regions + average all of all regions

CRBL: Cerebellar cortex | FCTX: Frontal cortex | HIPP: Hippocampus | MEDU: Medullar (inferior olivary nucleus) | OCTX: Occipital cortex | PUTM: Putamen | SNIG: Substantia nigra | TCTX: Temporal cortex | THAL: Thalamus | WHMT: intralobular white matter

NMF analysis for 1p36

Top two gene clusters from NMF analysis

Figure 6